

Evolution of RAN-core Convergence towards 6G: An Analysis of the Key Technologies, Principles and Challenges

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Abstract:

The adoption of cloud nativeness in the form of Service-Based Architecture (SBA) have played a significant role in shaping 5G networks. Despite these design architecture principles, the Radio Access Network (RAN) and Core Network (CN) were developed separately following different paradigms and thereby limiting the provision of end-to-end SBA in the Fifth Generation (5G) CN. Such logical separation accelerates the deployment of RAN and CN but at the same time it brings limitations in terms of duplicate functionalities, signaling overhead and complexity, since there is a need for coordination for enabling end-to-end processes, e.g., Quality of Service (QoS) provision. As the emerging use cases for the forthcoming Sixth Generation (6G) era rely on a tight cooperation of RAN and CN new innovative solutions are essential. This article highlights the main challenges behind RAN-CN convergence and derive the main principles behind RAN-CN convergence shedding light into different deployment options.

1- Introduction:

The adoption of SBA in the mobile CN have dramatically altered the landscape of 5G allowing a modular framework that focuses on discrete services instead of monolithic Network Functions (NFs) in where software and functionality were deployed on dedicated hardware. Consequently, SBA enhances the flexibility and scalability of the 5G core network. In the RAN, virtualization focused on base station design, i.e., splitting a generic Node B (gNB) into the Central Unit (CU) and one or more Distributed Units (DU) leveraging the benefits of cloud-RAN.

However, the notion of SBA in the RAN was not adopted despite that fact that was discussed in the context of the N2 interface, i.e., the interface between a base station and the core network, since it was considered as immature¹. The RAN and CN have been logically separated in both their design and standardization, even though CU consists of higher layer protocols that can be hosted in the same cloud as core NFs. RAN-CN convergence aims to logically integrate relevant RAN and core capabilities as a new cross-domain functionality with both RAN and CN logic or, while offering flexibility of deployment given the use case. In this regard, one key consideration that may impact the convergence of RAN and CN is how to address the tradeoff between the commonalities (e.g. cloudification) vs. specificities (e.g. deployment positions) of RAN and CN in real deployment environments.

With the advent of 6G use cases as documented in the IMT-2030 vision [1], new service requirements related to sensing, i.e., ISAC, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and QoS for new applications such as holographic teleportation, extended and mixed reality and metaverse accelerate the need for a new network design paradigm. Such network paradigm shall allow RAN to offer selected radio related functionalities which may be consumed by CN as RAN services and vice versa, or even introduce new NFs with converged RAN-CN functionality to enable easier and rapid reaction to address emerging end-

¹ 3GPP TSG SA2 Meeting #146E, Intel, Cisco, Verizon, Qualcomm, AT&T, DT, New Study on Service-based N2, Aug. 2021.

to-end 6G service requirements. The notion of a service in RAN is equivalent to a functionality in a RAN entity (CU, DU, RIC) which is produced by a RAN protocol function and can be consumed by another entity e.g. in RAN or CN.

A key enabler for RAN-CN convergence is the adoption and extension of SBA into the RAN, which would allow RAN to offer and consume network capabilities as services to or from the CN and vice versa. However, RAN-CN convergence is challenging due to the tight coupling and layered architecture of RAN protocols. A fundamental challenge to consider is how to decompose or rather, recompose the layered RAN protocol architecture into the SBA paradigm. Exposing raw radio parameters to the CN may also increase complexity since such parameters are not only provided in finer granularities but also from multiple RAN nodes.

Current efforts in RAN-CN convergence focus on categorizing RAN services in the control and user plane also including UE services [2], as well as on analyzing the principles behind SBA-RAN stating that RAN services should be highly cohesive, i.e. focus on one task, and be loosely coupled. O-RAN has also investigated the basic design principles of service-based RAN including service modularity, reusability, discovery and composition, secure access and more [3]. Also, in [4] a 6G RAN-core converged architecture is introduced integrating RAN CU with specific core network functions and a dedicated control plane network function for the CP signaling of each UE, demonstrating efficiency, scalability and flexibility benefits. These efforts engage on specific technology areas without considering the bigger picture on the design impact of SBA in the RAN and on the challenges when integrating with the CN. Furthermore, 6G-CLOUD project envisions an end-to-end service-oriented architecture where the SBA design for RAN is the key study item (enablers for implementing SBA extensions to RAN are being investigated) [5].

This paper provides an overarching view of RAN-CN convergence, providing the relevant background information and definitions and motivates the usage of RAN-CN convergence by considering the respective use cases that can benefit from it. It also investigates the main principles behind RAN-CN convergence and the respective network architecture design enhancement options for supporting RAN-CN convergence.

The rest of the article is structured as follows. Section 2 presents some representative use cases motivating the use of the RAN-CN convergence paradigm, while Section 3 discusses the background related to SBA and builds the notion of service-based RAN. Section 4 introduces the network architecture enhancements examining two different options, while Section 5 presents the main RAN-CN convergence design considerations and provides a quantitative evaluation of the different solutions. Section 6 discusses the forthcoming challenges. Finally, Section 7 concludes the paper.

2 – Key Drivers for RAN-CN Convergence in 6G

The vision of 5G was to empower verticals with network services offered via the means of virtualization, e.g., network softwarization and slicing. However, the focus of virtualization was on CN optimization and exposure. RAN and CN were treated separately potentially introducing performance barriers for services that require a tighter inter-operation of the RAN and CN, e.g., latency or QoS sensitive services or services that required real-time information exchange. The emerging 6G new use cases drive the need for an evolution towards a service-based RAN including RAN-CN convergence. Some of these emerging services include:

Converged RAN-CN QoS optimization

The provision of certain services such as Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) require the assurance of service continuity, which is based on awareness of the dynamics of network performance [6]. Network performance dynamics drive the QoS optimization. In 5G, core network specifications support alternative QoS profiles [7], where verticals can provide multiple QoS levels when requesting a service. The network then has the flexibility to adjust the QoS profile considering dynamic network conditions. The RAN can check and inform the CN when radio QoS is downgraded to align the QoS profile saving CN resources that otherwise would be wasted. When the radio conditions improve the RAN can trigger the CN for a QoS profile upgrade or rectification. Considering several QoS flows and alternative QoS profiles this process may provide to be complex introducing excessive signaling among the RAN and CN. With RAN-CN convergence, such feature can be further optimized using near-real time RAN measurements as a service which can be consumed by CN.

Cross-domain Analytics & AI/ML

Analytics and AI/ML in 5G rely on data collected from several different domains including the RAN. However, there is no direct interaction from the CN to the RAN and RAN performance measurements are currently collected from the Operations, Administration and Maintenance (OAM), which aggregates the measurements obtained from individual UEs, e.g., via Minimization of Drive Tests (MDT) procedures, on the cell level or tracking area level. To address this issue extension on the SBA towards the RAN was suggested in [8] to support end-to-end analytics. The support for cross-domain analytics/AI requires an architecture shift to joint design or RAN/CN capabilities to allow better synergy of RAN and CN AI/analytics functionalities. Indeed, a converged RAN and CN would enable RAN services related to performance measurements or RAN analytics to be consumed by the CN directly and vice versa, enabling real-time information exchange with fine granular radio measurements related to specific UE locations within a cell. RAN-CN convergence may also encourage joint AI/ML model training and/or split of the inference among the RAN and CN introducing flexibility on the applicability of analytics for the emerging 6G services.

Integrated Communications and Sensing

ISAC, based on the 3GPP Stage 1 standardization (TS 22.137), allows the inclusion of sensing capabilities in a communication network by taking advantage of the reflections of transmitted signals to obtain information related to the shape, size, orientation, speed, location, or distances between objects not necessarily equipped with a sim card. According to 3GPP TR [23.700-14](#), ISAC reflections of a transmitted sensing signal are received by several radio entities, which are forwarded to a sensing NF. Such sensing NF is responsible for selecting and managing the optimal receiving sensing entities, processing the collected data using AI/ML capabilities to determine the sensing target and its corresponding characteristics and facilitating exposure capabilities towards 3rd parties that request sensing services. A service-based RAN may allow the selection of RAN entities for sensing purposes, while the introduction of a sensing NF as a RAN-CN converged NF can simplify the coordination of RAN entities involved and the radio signal collection, as well as the AI/ML processing for identifying a sensing target and exposing the result to a 3rd party.

3 – Service Based Architecture & RAN-CN Convergence

The origins of SBA are based on the concept of Service-Oriented Architecture (SOA), which introduced the notion of a service as an independent unit of functionality related to a networking job or an application component. Services can be self-contained i.e., act and maintained separately and can cooperate with one another to perform a specific task. An evolution of the SOA occurred with the advent of microservices, which can interact over a medium using lightweight protocols, e.g., HTTP.

A microservice architecture is the technology behind the advent of SBA in 5G CN, which can provide a further degree of flexibility and scalability. SBA is based on a consumer-producer model in where NFs can select, request, and receive or offer a service upon a specified condition. A service producer maintains one or more services and is responsible for making them available by registering them in a repository, i.e., Network Repository Function (NRF), together with their usage description. The NRF assists other NFs to identify and select a service as illustrated in Figure 1. A service consumer can then discover a service from the NRF using the service description metadata. It can then select an NF as service producer, which matched best its request and issue a service request to bind and use a service.

Figure 1: Overview of the service registration and discovery process within 5G SBA.

A key enabler in RAN-CN convergence is the extension of service-based architecture to the RAN side, since the convergence of functionalities spanning across RAN and CN may be eased by the service-oriented design principles. To enable a service-based RAN architecture, there is a need to specify the concept of a RAN function or RAN NF responsible to offer RAN services or equivalently RAN-CN converged function that offers both RAN and CN services. Additionally, there is a need to define the notion of a RAN service. A RAN service may comprise a configuration, control or monitoring capability, which can be provided by RAN NF or a RAN-CN converged function and may include:

- Radio Resource Management (RRM) related services such as: inter-cell RRM, connection mobility control, radio bearer control, MAC scheduling, traffic steering etc.
- Radio connection control services such as radio bear management or mobile terminal radio connectivity.
- RAN control services enabled by SBA, such as xApp type of service, or Decentralized Self-Organized Network (D-SON) services executed in the base station, such as: handover and mobility robustness optimization, mobility load balancing, etc.
- AI/ML services for supporting ML-enabled RAN analytics, e.g., inference or training based on local RAN or UE data.
- RAN capability exposure services, e.g., RAN performance measurements, RAN parameter configuration capabilities, gateway capabilities.

RAN services shall be produced by a RAN NF or RAN-CN function and consumed by another including also conventional core NFs taking advantage of the SBA paradigm. RAN-CN convergence can be realized by a joint functionality that consists of components that have both RAN and CN logic, which can be deployed as a: (i) collocated NF, (ii) new converged NF or (iii) service logic that can be available from the RAN to the CN, i.e., from a RAN NF to 5G core NF, and vice versa in a service-based manner.

4–RAN-CN Convergence Architecture Considerations

The impact of RAN-CN convergence depends on how convergence appears in the SBA architecture and what does convergence represent. In principle, there are two different directions echoing the discussion in [3]: (i) an incremental approach that introduces an abstraction layer to represent RAN services without the need to modify the RAN ensuring backward compatibility with 5G, and (ii) a disruptive approach that extend the SBA paradigm towards the RAN.

There can be different ways to achieve the integration between RAN and CN. Two possible options which are presented in Fig. 2 are the following:

- In Option 1, the RAN is not service-based, and to enable the integration with Core, we envision a Service-based Integration Layer (SBIL) to instantiate, and register RAN produced services which are abstracted (e.g. for monitoring and control operations). Such an option can be adopted in the industry in 6G deployments from Day 1 since it doesn't have implications on the existing 5G RAN protocols, requires mainly CN enhancements and is interoperable with BSs of previous generations. In this option, the control fabric is assumed to be within the SBIL. This option addresses the performance barrier for services that require a tighter and simple inter-operation of RAN and CN, by introducing SBIL as a middleware entity for abstracting RAN services which monitor the low layers and exposing to CN only if there is an alerting situation (e.g. high interference).
- In Option 2, the RAN is service-based, and the figure sketches an example of RAN NF services, e.g., CU service, DU services, RIC and xApp services. SBIL can be an additional set of services for RAN capability exposure and abstraction. SBIL in that case will support alleviating the impact of different function granularities between RAN and CN, by providing a layer for processing and abstracting before exposing RAN services to CN. Here to note, that there can be different deployments of services, as discussed above (e.g., RAN CP NF, RAN Ctrl Apps, etc.) and this is just an example deployment. In this option, there are two ways of integrating the RAN services with the Core Network:
 1. Via SBIL which is like a proxy/gateway to core network and supports the registration and discovery of RAN services. So, RAN NF/services are not directly part of the core SBA.
 2. RAN services can directly register and be available at the Core SBA; hence SBIP may be optional for providing some abstraction as complementary functionality when necessary.

Figure 2: 6G-Cloud RAN – Core convergence options

In this figure, SBIL is being investigated as an optional new capability for supporting RAN and Core integration. SBIL allows the evolution of SBA without providing strict requirements on changing completely the RAN architecture and can also work with 5G NR and LTE radio access. CN interaction with the SBIL using a new SBI, allows direct interfacing with CN NFs being able to consume RAN services provided (or relayed) by SBIL. SBIL can be deployed per Area of Interest, a smaller targeted area or even in specific gNBs providing freedom on its adoption. The SBIL functionalities include among others:

- Gateway functionality at RAN (acts as an entity like CAPIF for RAN service/API exposure)
- Chaining / grouping capability of RAN services based on consumer requirements.
- Monitoring capability and reporting.
- Registering RAN services on behalf of RAN (including one or more CUs/DUs/RUs).
- Assisting in the discovery and selection process of RAN services
- RAN context building and abstraction to ease the interaction with Core and AF/Servers which “speak different language”.

SBIL in certain implementations, receives the UE/RAN parameters and translates them to actions / events which are perceivable by the Consumer NF (e.g., high load indication, RAN UE KPI reaching a low threshold) if the RAN service is about RAN performance.

In addition, the SBIL may support building RAN context at RAN and will have the benefit of processing real-time measurements (e.g., CSI/CQI). Example RAN context building is that SBIL receives RAN / UE context (e.g., L2 measurements) from RAN and processes and abstracts to UE QoE / QoS downgrade indication, or High resource load indication or High RAN delay indication etc.

5–RAN-CN Convergence Design Considerations

This section introduces a set of considerations in investigating and deriving the design principles behind RAN-CN convergence and service-based RAN. Table 1 summarizes the benefits and shortcomings of each design consideration.

Table 1: Benefits and shortcomings of the RAN-CN convergence considerations

Principle	Benefits	Shortcomings / Challenges
Convergence granularity option: (i) service, (ii) function	(i) flexible and easier to deploy, (ii) co-located functionalities can reduce signaling and latency.	(i) may introduce latency and overhead depending on usage (ii) lacks flexibility in design and exposing RAN services in a finer granular manner.
Control plane Vs Data plane	Joint decision and information exposure Vs direct packet processing and forwarding.	Indirect impact on network based on interpretation of information, Vs increase complexity, requires disruptive protocol changes.
Impact on RAN Architecture	Simple, distributed architecture, that optimize services and increase flexibility.	Flat architecture is complex since it needs enhancements in NF logic and protocols.
Service discovery and selection	Assist to identify a service from the radio to the core and vice versa.	Enhancements needed in NRF or in introducing a new RAN service repository.
Exposure capabilities	Applications can directly consume and configure converged and RAN services.	Security and abstraction aspects need to be enhanced.
Configuring converged RAN-CN services	Converged RAN-CN service and NFs configured optimally.	Complexity of cross-domain management is increased.
Configuration of Non-Access Stratum (NAS)	New converged services providing decentralization and cross-layer optimization.	Complex NAS enhancements need intelligence support.

Consideration 1: Granularity of RAN-CN convergence

Given the advancement made in 5G and depending on how the emerging 6G architecture would be specified, the RAN-CN convergence design can vary considering two different granularities: (i) at the service level, and (ii) at the function level.

At the service level, the notion of a converged service is enabled by extending the SBA to the RAN allowing the capability to request and consume a RAN NF component, aka a service, from the CN and vice versa for collaborative decision-making. The roles of service producer and consumer can be facilitated by both RAN and CN facilitating convergence in both directions, but their usage requires discovery and selection that may introduce latency.

At the function level, RAN-CN convergence involves the design of a single NF that contains both RAN and CN logic simultaneously. Such converged capability may assist in performing a RAN operation from a CN NF, e.g., selecting RAN entities for receiving the reflected sensing signals.

Different granularities support different use cases, where the service-level granularity is closer to micro-service based architecture, which is being used in IT domain, this may require shifting the SBA design in 5G CN (which supports function level SBA). This may require enhancements in 6G SBA in both RAN and CN domains. On the other hand, the function-level granularity is close to 5G SBA notion, however this lacks flexibility of designing and exposing RAN services in a finer granular manner.

Consideration 2: Convergence at user plane vs. control plane

RAN-CN convergence may impact both user and control plane in different manners. In the control plane, convergence impact joint decisions and information exposure, while in the user plane it relates to packet processing and forwarding.

When convergence is realized on a functional level, it may also be across control and user plane, i.e., by realized in both control and user planes. For instance, in a converged RAN-CN NF, the CU-CP functions may be integrated with CN NFs (e.g., AMF) to design converged control plane services, while CU-UP may be merged with User Plane Function (UPF) to realize converged user plane services [9]. Another example can be the direct mapping of IP flows to Data Radio Bearers (DRBs), replacing the two-step mapping of IP flows-to-QoS flows-to-DRB between the UE and the data network by introducing a merged functionality of both RAN and CN sides enabling efficient protocol operations [10].

Consideration 3: Impact on RAN architecture

The impact of convergence in the RAN architecture may introduce simplification for processes but would also require certain enhancements.

Convergence may eliminate gating, e.g., control plane of CU and AMF, to reduce a single anchor connectivity across RAN and CN, allowing DUs to interact with the CN NFs directly via an SBA medium without the need to transverse the CU and AMF. This approach requires a re-distribution of certain functionalities that were eliminated to other RAN and CN NFs.

Simplification may also be achieved via combining equivalent functionality of RAN and CN, e.g., a unified access and mobility function related to both RAN and CN or QoS mapping across the RAN and CN. Such unified functions may also share user context, which may allow stateless NFs but requires certain protocol enhancements.

Consideration 4: Service discovery and selection in converged RAN-CN architecture

In a converged RAN-CN there is the need to initially represent RAN services and/or RAN NFs to allow their discovery and selection based on RAN capabilities, permissions, interoperability and usage or status information. This can be achieved either by introducing a RAN NF in where certain RAN services are associated, or a RAN NF that represents a middleware entity, i.e., SBIL, which abstracts the underlying RAN services.

To enable the discovery and selection of RAN services and/or RAN NFs, a new RAN profile is needed to capture the RAN service capabilities including:

- RAN service status information related to service availability or failure.
- Authorization and/or permissions related to the consumer type.
- Serving scope of the radio access points related to the geographical coverage of a RAN NF.
- Priority and load information, to assist in selecting the appropriate RAN NF and/or RAN service, i.e., in case of overlapping coverage for load balancing purposes.
- Radio specific capabilities that may relate to the radio access technology, antenna characteristics and spectrum information and/or to radio transmission specific features related to carrier aggregation, coordinated multipoint operation, or support of dual steering.
- Interoperability information, i.e., vendor specific information.

Such RAN NF profile shall be registered in a service repository. This repository can be realized by the NRF in the CN that may need to hold both RAN NF and CN information. In this case, the RAN NF represents SBIL. Alternatively, a new RAN repository can hold RAN NF services assisting service

discovery in the RAN with SBIL being the mediator with NRF when a core NF needs a RAN service and vice versa.

Consideration 5: Exposure capabilities of a converged RAN-CN architecture

Exposure capabilities are currently facilitated using the Network Exposure Function (NEF) that authorize, and abstract services offered to verticals. Verticals may consume network information and mobile network services but with the advent of SBA towards the RAN, verticals may be able to consume RAN services interacting with the RAN directly. RAN exposure capabilities may also enable RAN service selection or provision, e.g., an RRM scheduler. RAN parameters need also to be understood by verticals, e.g., how they may impact a service, or need to be consolidated if these parameters are exposed from several different RAN nodes related to a single service.

RAN specific NEF enhancements are needed to harden security, enable RAN abstraction and introduce RAN configuration capabilities, e.g., RAN service provision. NEF enhancements are also needed to convert RAN information into meaningful data for verticals.

Consideration 6: Configuration of the RAN-CN converged NFs

The configuration of RAN and CN is currently being carried out by a dedicated management function. With the advent of converged RAN-CN functions there is a need to also modify the OAM to: (i) allow the configuration of combined RAN and CN services, (ii) deploy the converged RAN-CN NFs at optimal locations, and (iii) take care of the life cycle management, which introduces increased complexity since RAN and CN services may have different needs and operate at different granularities. Managing converged RAN-CN NFs in the OAM can be achieved by enhancing the cross-domain manager that considers both RAN and CN functions.

Consideration 7: Configuration of Non-Access Stratum (NAS)

When designing RAN and core convergence, the role and behavior of the NAS will be influenced by the integration of access and core functions. NAS functions, such as mobility management and session management, will need to support a converged control plane. The shift towards decentralized and distributed network architectures, including edge computing, will require NAS protocols to adapt for efficient signaling in localized and distributed environments. The integration of AI/ML for predictive mobility and session optimization will enhance NAS capabilities. Additionally, NAS signaling must incorporate feedback from the RAN for cross-layer optimization, enabling decisions such as QoS adjustments and efficient paging.

6 – Open Challenges

Although several solutions are introduced for RAN-CN convergence, the evolution towards service-based RAN and RAN-CN convergence poses several open challenges including the following:

Compatibility with conventional architecture: The evolution towards full service-based architecture poses challenges related to the implementation together with existing (5G, 4G) cellular systems which do not support RAN-CN convergence and it may require further investigation on limitations (in both infrastructure and interfaces) in non-standalone 6G deployments and in scenarios where 6G is non-uniformly deployed within a PLMN.

Limitations of lower RAN layer protocols: The feasibility of applying the service-based paradigm in the lower layer protocols of RAN is still debatable, since the operational latency requirement of the MAC

layer is 100 microseconds and lower PHY layers is 250 microseconds [11], while the time granularity of the CN is in the order of seconds or minutes. Such disparity in terms of latency may further increase the complexity of convergence.

Unified data collection/distribution interface: With the introduction of service-based RAN, more measurements would be available. Since current performance measurements from the different domains, i.e., CN, OAM, and application, employ different interfaces with distinct mechanisms for collecting and distributing data there is an increased complexity when cross-domain data is needed, e.g., for analytics. A unified interface to collect and distribute data irrespective of the domain would introduce simplicity, but its design to accommodate diverse needs and deployment is challenging.

Compute capabilities in the RAN: The RAN is arguably the most compute-intensive part of the mobile network. On top of that, 6G enabling technologies such as sensing, video AI processing, will stress further the computing power limits of the RAN. However, compute power is not so easily scalable as it gets closer in the RAN, besides the security concerns.

7- Conclusion

This article laid down the motivation and general considerations related to the introduction of RAN-CN convergence for the emerging 6G network. Certain representative use cases that may benefit from convergence are analyzed followed by an extensive review of related work. This article derives the fundamental principles behind convergence and summarizes the architecture impact and open challenges that should be addressed to assist the evolution and industry adoption of RAN-CN convergence in 6G.

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